

Modular Programme for Education and Training
YOUTH SPORT COACH

M#5 Hands-on Coaching

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>

<p>2</p>	<p>Principles of Coaching Children</p>	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills and Play</p>	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Hands-on Coaching</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p>

		<p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Hands-on Coaching
Module Number	5
Core Module Aim	The aim of the core module is to help craft safe learning experiences as a core aspect of coach education programs. “You learn how to coach by coaching” – with this in mind, a key element of continued coach learning should be hands-on coaching experiences that provide coach learners with a safe space where they can prepare coaching experiences, engage in coaching practice, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection.
Module Description	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Youth Sport Coaches through creating safe spaces and learning environments where direct participation in learning activities helps YSCs to learn and grow in their coaching. Through a hands-on approach, participants will be enabled to incorporate key concepts and competencies in their hands-on coaching experience.</p> <p>During the module Youth Sport Coaches will be familiarized with key principles underlying effective coaching practice and develop their key coaching skills/tools. They will then have an opportunity to engage in real-life/role-play coaching and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the lessons learned to their coaching practice. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours (including 11 hours of Self-Directed Learning; <i>plus an optional 20 hrs of Coaching Work Placement</i>)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	Class based and field based presentations, during which coaches will be involved in experiencing practical coaching skills (plan, organize, observe, demonstrate, analyse, provide feedback, evaluate), in a preliminary way, so as to contribute to the sporting process as an assistant coach. After hands-on coaching experience, reflection on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values, individually, as a group of co-coaches and with a mentor
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) • ICOACHKIDS – The Coaches’ Toolkit • ICOACHKIDS – ICK Essentials Modules • ICOACHKIDS – Growing Coaches • Sport New Zealand Balance is Better - Designing a Session – Understanding the Three Rs: Repetition, Realism, and Relevance • Sport New Zealand Balance is Better – Praise vs. Affirmation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sport New Zealand Balance is Better - What Can We Learn from the Coaching Philosophies of Five Great Coaches? • Sport New Zealand Balance is Better – Developing Your Coaching Identity • Bengoechea et al. (2004). Understanding and promoting fun in youth sport: coaches’ perspectives • Van Mullem, P., & Gano-Overway, L. (2021). <i>To be a better coach: A guide for the youth sport coach and coach developer</i>. Rowman & Littlefield 	
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes	
Module structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 5.1: Fundamentals of Coaching Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units • Course 5.2: Preparing Hands-on Coaching Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 5.3: Hands-on Coaching Experience & Debrief <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5 h Practical Experience ○ 5 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 5 h Self-Directed Working hours ○ <i>Optional: 20 h Coaching Work Placement</i> 	
Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learner-centred coaching • Group dynamics & Social interaction • Importance of play & exploration • Children’s interests & preferences 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting fun & enjoyment • Communication skills • Teaching / pedagogical skills • Active listening • Conflict management skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect for children’s needs and interests • Empathy and patience • Fun and enjoyment • Enthusiasm and Motivation • Creativity 	<p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect and Fair Play • Inclusion and cooperation • Fun & enjoyment • Empathy • Ethical behavior
Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):	

	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic motor development knowledge • Basic games knowledge • Basics of social interaction and group dynamics • Importance of play and exploration 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Creativity • Listening skills • Cooperation skills • Problem solving skills
	<p>Attitudes:</p> <p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curiosity and creativity • Empathy and patience • Cooperation • Enthusiasm, fun and enjoyment 	<p>Values:</p> <p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect and Fair Play • Fun & enjoyment • Cooperation
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 2: Principles of coaching children • Module 6: Plan, reflect and learn 	

Course Structure

Course Title	Fundamentals to Coaching Practice		
Course Number	5.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand and relate to key coaching models and frameworks for Youth Sport - Identify key strengths and growth areas in their current coaching practice - Engage with Coaching Toolkits to effectively explain, demonstrate, set up, stand back, question, listen and engage with feedback on coaching practice 		
Course Structure	L	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Models and frameworks for coaching practice
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: Reflecting on personal coaching experience and context
	W	3 h	Teaching Unit 3: Aligning personal coaching experience with coaching models and frameworks
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing the Youth Sport Compass model: development-oriented, motivational, socially-safe, and caring coaching • Children are not mini-adults: make sport fit the child, not the child fit the sport • SPEC model (Lara-Bercial, 2012): non-linear development along cognitive, social, physical, emotional bean, impacted by chronological, biological, and training ages. • Coaching Zones: Boredom, Comfort, Learning and Panic zones • The Multi-Skills Jigsaw (Lara-Bercial et al., 2015) • What do children want from a coach • Building relationships • Identifying differences and different needs in children/learners • Motivation: What do children want from sport (it's NOT competing all the time...) • Building Blocks towards a motivated and confident child in sport • The Coach's Toolkit: Explanations, Demonstrations, Setting up and Standing back, Questioning and Listening, Feedback and Reflection 	

<p>Course Content (examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</p>	<p>TU 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch Youth Sport Compass video and reflect on how it relates to your current coaching experience https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83McfP3FUOk • Reflect on how the SPEC model relates to your current coaching practice: How are you considering and supporting cognitive, social, physical, and emotional development • Complete the ICOACHKIDS Course 3 “Coaching on the Ground: Planning, Doing and Reviewing” and complete the Study Guides • Watch the Coach’s Toolkit videos on the ICOACHKIDS website. Then download the handouts and reflect on how well your coaching practice currently aligns with these recommendations
	<p>TU 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small group discussion: how is each of you creating a positive environment where children can thrive by using the Youth Sport Compass model? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them? • Small group discussion: how does the SPEC model relate to your current coaching practice and how are you considering and supporting cognitive, social, physical, and emotional development? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them? • Group discussion: Understanding the wants and needs of children is essential to any coach. These wants and needs are factors that underpin successful learning. How do you identify wants and needs of the children you coach? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them?

Course Title	Preparing Hands-on Coaching Practice		
Course Number	5.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effectively prepare for a specific hands-on coaching experience, by engaging with specific reflection, and preparation - Apply Progressive Game Builds strategies - Use recycling strategies effectively to optimize session flow - Prepare for How? And What? to observe, and how to provide feedback 		
Course Structure	W	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: What do we bring to coaching?
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: My Coaching Session Planner
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete and discuss “What are You Bringing to Your Coaching” worksheet (Values/Beliefs, Sport Experiences, Education, Life Experience/Learning, Other things... What does each of those experiences bring to your coaching?) • Complete and discuss “Coaches Learn Best” worksheet • Revisit/revise/create your coaching philosophy: A coaching philosophy provides a set of explicit guidelines on how to translate your core values and beliefs into actions. As such, it is inherently practical: it allows you to plan, deliver and reflect more effectively. The Youth Sport Compass and ICoachKids Pledge offer foundations for a sound coaching philosophy. • Engaging with the Coach Toolkit framework for session preparation: What are your learning intentions? What activities will you implement to achieve those outcomes? How will you use Progressive Game Builds and Recycling? How are you implementing the Voice of the Child? How will you Explain, Demonstrate, Set up, Stand back, Question and Listen, provide Feedback, Reflect (during the session)? 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read, watch and reflect on the information about the Lifelong Learning Coach on the ICOACHKIDS website • Engage with the issue-specific Online Tool to create a specific image and affirmations that will ground and guide you during your coaching session, supporting your coaching philosophy. • Complete the Coaching Session Planner 1 to specifically map out your coaching session 	

Course Title	Hands-on Coaching Experience & Debrief		
Course Number	5.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Put the session plan into action - Reflect on the hands-on coaching experience, and get feedback from peers/mentors/coach developers - Plan a revised coaching session and put it into action with a peer coaching approach - Reflect on amended session 2, and get feedback from peers/mentors/coach developers 		
Course Structure	PE	5 h	Teaching Unit 1: Hands-on coaching experience
	W	5 h	Teaching Unit 2: Reflection, feedback, and revision of hands-on coaching experience
	SDL	5 h	Teaching Unit 3: Lessons-learned and additional learning opportunities for continued learning and growth
	SDL	20 h	Teaching Unit 4: Coaching Work Placement
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set-up and do your hands-on coaching session 1 • Debrief your session1 group • Personal reflection on hands-on coaching session 1 • Set-up and do your hands-on coaching session 2 • Debrief your session2 group • Personal reflection on hands-on coaching session 2 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Debrief of hands-on coaching session 1 (and session 2, subsequently): use reflection models like “two stars (positives), one wish (growth spot)” or the KISS model (Keep, Increase, Stop, Start) • Discuss self-reflection and observer feedback on session 1 (and session 2, subsequently) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Where does it align, differ? • What are specific improvement goals for session 2? • Complete the Coaching Session Planner 2 to specifically map out your coaching session for amended peer-coaching session 	

	<p>TU 3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in specific reflection “on practice” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How did your coaching philosophy help you? ○ How did you hear “The Voice of the Child”? ○ What did you apply and what worked from the Youth Sport Compass climate model? ○ Which Coach’s Toolkit parts did you use and how well did you apply them? • What are Personal Learnings from the hands-on coaching experience? • What are Personal Improvement Goals after your hands-on coaching experience? • Watch the ICOACHKIDS video on “Behavior Change Tips for Coaches” • Explore the ICOACHKIDS “Your Learning as a Coach” resources
	<p>TU 4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in 10 coaching sessions with 2 hrs each to plan, deliver, and reflect as part of a Coaching Work-Placement program. Maintain a Coaching Diary to track planning, organisation, delivery, reflection, and learning on each coaching session; add reflections on overall placement and overall learnings